

Predictive data analytics for bioenergy generation planning and operation

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INTRODUCTION:

Driven by the global shift towards low carbon economy and national energy priorities, the clean energy generation from renewable sources is experiencing a growing demand. Bioenergy derived from wood and other biomass feedstocks is an attractive option in clean energy generation. Locally available biomass and residues can be converted to heat and power for local communities enabling local socio-economic development. Bioenergy is a viable and sustainable solution for off-grid markets such as Canadian remote communities. However, the decision makers within communities, investment firms and entrepreneurs are faced with a bewildering array of competing yet unproven technologies, when it comes to implementation of bioenergy solutions. Decisions regarding feedstock availability, delivery logistics and costs, economic profitability, greenhouse gas emissions and carbon taxes and power and heat demand need to be made at every step of a project, including planning, execution and operation.

The data analytics team at NRC's bioenergy program is currently developing predictive analytic tools and techniques to provide insights and to make data intensive decisions. Recently, we have developed a tool using machine learning to predict the solid and bio-degradable waste generation at municipal level. This tool is based on an artificial neural network model trained on past data and uses socio-economic parameters to predict waste generation where such data is non-existing. Hence, this tool provides critical data on biomass availability at regional level for bioenergy generation. This machine learning tool is part of a techno-economic analysis (TEA) to rank clean energy solution based on technical, financial, environmental and social criteria. We will provide a ranking of best available technology in the context of bioenergy solutions for rural and remote communities.

AIM:

To accurately predict municipal solid waste (MSW) generation and diversion based on demographic and socio-economic parameters at municipal level.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Past waste generation data for 220 municipalities in Ontario, Canada was collected and assembled into datasets. Demographic and socio-economic variables of municipalities were derived from Canadian census program data. Data was integrated and processed to remove outliers and errors. The relevant features to be included in the model were selected according to correlation coefficient ranking. Neural network algorithms was then used to generate models that

maps socio-economic variables into waste generation variables. The models created were tested using unseen data.

RESULTS:

The most relevant features selected for the waste generation models were the age structure, income and housing size. Machine learning algorithms were successfully applied to build generalized waste generation models. The models created were able to predict waste generation with 72% accuracy for out-of-sample data at municipal level.

CONCLUSIONS:

This study demonstrates the feasibility of creating tools that helps regional planning by sourcing, pre-processing, integrating and modeling publically available data. Predicting the waste generation provides a unique opportunity to plan waste management and residue utilization operations. It also provides critical data for Canadian remote regions energy planning.

KEYWORDS:

Bioenergy, solid waste; machine learning; neural networks, forecasting

BIOGRAPHY:

Miyuru Kannangara is a modeling and analytics expert with experience in renewable energy, biorefinery and biofuel research. Before joining NRC, he pursued his PhD research at Ecole Polytechnique de Montreal in biorefinery process development and integration. His experience encompasses techno-economic analysis, process simulation, GHG modeling and machine learning.

Miyuru joined NRC EME in March 2016 as a research associate for the Materials Assessment team. He has been involved in projects on cost analysis of bioenergy/biorefinery products, biorefinery process simulation, biomass logistics cost modeling, machine learning for biomass availability modeling and GHG modeling of grid electricity storage.